

Enabling Ecological Survey Data Integration with the Humboldt Extension to Darwin Core

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Abstract

In the face of the global biodiversity crisis, accessibility to biodiversity data that is maximally effective for downstream use in science, conservation, and policy is paramount. The Darwin Core standard has played a central role in providing a standardised structure and vocabulary for biodiversity data. However, early iterations of the standard were not optimised to capture the sampling context of biodiversity surveys—survey methods, scope, and sampling effort—which is essential for the correct interpretation and potential reuse of such data. To address this limitation, we present the Humboldt Extension to Darwin Core, a ratified standard designed to accommodate datasets that contain such contextual information. Building upon an initial,

36 previously developed framework, we significantly improved, fully tested, and ratified a final
37 standard, following a community process defined by Biodiversity Information Standards
38 (TDWG), an international standards organisation. The resulting Humboldt Extension adds 55
39 terms that enrich the Darwin Core, providing the terms needed to capture and share multiple
40 types of biodiversity survey data. We illustrate the benefits of implementing the Humboldt
41 Extension with three case studies and demonstrate how richer data can be used in research,
42 modelling, and to inform decision-making. We urge the uptake and use of this Extension to
43 facilitate the reuse and synthesis of monitoring data, particularly structured surveys and
44 inventories, for science, conservation, and policy.

45

46 Keywords

47 biodiversity monitoring, data standards, ecological inventories, FAIR data, sampling design

48 Introduction

49 Biodiversity loss presents a critical threat to global health and ecosystems, exacerbated by
50 unsustainable human activities that accelerate species extinction (Cardinale et al. 2012, IPBES
51 2019, Wilson 1988, WWF 2024). Despite significant advancements in our understanding of
52 biodiversity and nature's essential contributions to human well-being (Costanza et al. 1998,
53 Daily 1999), the urgency of the crisis demands immediate action. Policymakers and
54 governments have responded with commitments such as the United Nations Convention on
55 Biological Diversity (CBD) and the establishment of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy
56 Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) to navigate these challenges. In
57 December 2022, the CBD adopted the historic Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity

58 Framework (GBF) to halt and reverse biodiversity loss by 2050, incorporating a monitoring
59 mechanism to track progress towards its ambitious targets and rectify shortcomings of previous
60 efforts, such as the Aichi Biodiversity Targets (Buchanan et al. 2020, Tittensor et al. 2014). The
61 effectiveness of this framework hinges upon the availability of robust biodiversity data necessary
62 for measuring progress (Affinito et al. 2024). Consequently, the biodiversity monitoring
63 community should enhance data collection and sharing following FAIR principles—findability,
64 accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (Wilkinson et al. 2016)—while fostering
65 infrastructures that facilitate access and sharing of *in situ* data and local datasets to meet the
66 GBF's monitoring requirements (Bisby 2000, Heberling et al. 2021).

67 The use of standardised vocabularies and common data structures underlies the success of
68 large biodiversity data infrastructures, such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF
69 2025a, <https://www.gbif.org/>) and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS 2025,
70 <https://obis.org/>). Established in 2001, GBIF provides access to over 113,000 datasets
71 comprising more than three billion species occurrences documented by more than 2,400
72 institutions (as of May 2025). OBIS, launched in 2004, is a global open-access data and
73 information clearing house on marine biodiversity, hosting 5,719 datasets with over 137.5 million
74 occurrence records (as of May 2025).

75 At the heart of these biodiversity platforms are publishing systems that use the Darwin Core
76 standard (DwC, Wieczorek et al. 2012), which is maintained by an international organisation,
77 the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG, formerly the Taxonomic Databases Working
78 Group). DwC was originally developed to facilitate the interchange of information about the
79 occurrence of organisms and taxa, focusing on standardising data and metadata from natural
80 history collections. It therefore has focused on “species occurrences” and how, when, where
81 and by whom those occurrences were recorded. DwC is most suitable for incidentally recorded
82 occurrences, lacking the granular reporting of the data collection process required for semi-

83 structured and structured surveying. Still, it has been expanded and improved to include
84 additional key concepts and data types, and is managed by an active maintenance group that
85 continues to improve and extend the standard (Robertson et al. 2014). DwC has proven to be
86 the lynchpin standard for sharing species occurrence data and promoting biodiversity research
87 because it enables interoperability of data. To date, over 13,000 peer-reviewed publications
88 have used GBIF-mediated data to advance global biodiversity research and management (GBIF
89 2025b).

90 The “presence-only” data standardised and made interoperable through DwC, while
91 undoubtedly of value (*e.g.*, for species distribution modelling), also possess significant
92 limitations (Guillera-Arroita et al. 2015, Jetz et al. 2012). Knowing where species were detected
93 but also where they were not detected (*i.e.*, reported counts of zero) enables more accurate and
94 precise estimates of realised species distributions (Elith et al. 2006; Johnston et al. 2021).
95 Similarly, accounting for differences in the sampling or observation process leading to records
96 enables better estimates of distribution, relative abundance (Johnston et al. 2021), and trends in
97 abundance over time (Fink et al. 2023). In combination, records of zero detections and
98 information about the sampling process can be used to estimate the proportion of zero counts
99 that represent true absences, and not merely the failure to detect a taxon that was present but
100 undetected. Some analytical methods (MacKenzie et al. 2002, Royle 2004) additionally require
101 repeated surveys of target taxa at each of a set of locations, such that data are structured
102 hierarchically (*e.g.*, with individual sampling events nested within survey sites).. While some of
103 these types of information can be reported using DwC, it may not fully capture aspects such as
104 the absence of detections, taxonomic scope, variations in the data collection process (*e.g.*,
105 sampling effort), or hierarchical structure. Such information may exist, but it is typically shared
106 as part of the metadata in an unstructured manner, limiting the survey's proper interpretation
107 and potential re-use (Guralnick et al. 2018). The lack of a standardised vocabulary to describe

108 biodiversity surveys is a persistent barrier to their integration and broadest reuse. This limitation,
109 for instance, constitutes a key challenge for deriving some of the Essential Biodiversity
110 Variables (EBV) useful for monitoring biodiversity with high accuracy (Jetz et al. 2019, Pereira et
111 al. 2013). In particular, understanding trends in occupancy and abundance over time is critical
112 for assessing species and population health (Jetz et al. 2019), but in most cases requires semi-
113 structured or structured monitoring and its associated metadata (Kelling et al. 2019).

114 To fill the need for a richer vocabulary by which to capture and share biodiversity survey data
115 and metadata, Guralnick et al. (2018) proposed a new standard: the Humboldt Core. This
116 proposal was an initial step towards standardising the capture of information about the data
117 collection process and aimed to lay the foundations for a broader effort. Here, we describe the
118 outcome of a subsequent community-driven process to develop a standardised vocabulary for
119 capturing the sampling context of biodiversity survey data, specifically focusing on enabling a
120 proper description of the data collection process such that the data are interpretable and
121 interoperable. This formal process was accomplished by a Task Group within TDWG, following
122 a robust procedure (Vocabulary Maintenance Specification Task Group 2017). We describe how
123 and why the Humboldt Core evolved into the Humboldt Extension for Ecological Inventories
124 (<https://eco.tdwg.org/>), and we demonstrate how its implementation supports biodiversity data
125 sharing. A key outcome described here is a comprehensive set of terms that facilitate explicit
126 capture of the information needed to understand a survey design (*i.e.*, information related to
127 survey scope, effort, and completeness) to enable proper downstream integration and analysis.
128 The results also contain three implementation case studies, and we discuss the implications of
129 adopting the Humboldt Extension for data collection, curation, analyses, and further applications
130 in policy and conservation.

131 Methods

132 Biodiversity surveys

133 Biodiversity surveys and inventories (we will use these terms interchangeably) are systematic
134 processes for identifying and cataloguing the taxa present within a specific area. Because of
135 their systematic structure and design, surveys can effectively reveal species coexistence and
136 absence patterns if the sampling design and effort are appropriate relative to the intended
137 taxonomic and spatiotemporal scopes (Guralnick et al. 2018). These key descriptors of the data
138 collection process have to be reported in a standardised and structured way if users are to
139 interpret and reuse survey data accurately.

140 Guralnick et al. (2018) identified three types of survey data, and they contrasted these with
141 'incidental data' - obtained via opportunistic sampling, lacking structured design and taxonomic
142 scope, with no information on non-detections (e.g., museum specimens, incidental citizen
143 science data). An 'elementary inventory' refers to a single sampling event with a limited
144 spatiotemporal scope (e.g., surveys composed of a single net sweep, trap, transect or point
145 count). An 'extended inventory' involves repeated sampling events that aggregate data over
146 broader temporal or spatial scales (e.g., multi-point or transect sampling surveys, long term
147 vegetation surveys, algal sampling in water monitoring). Both survey types provide explicit
148 details on sampling protocols, spatial boundaries, and expectations for targeted organisms. At a
149 higher aggregation level, a 'compilation' merges studies employing different data collection
150 processes (such as sampling events combined with literature searches), often involving larger
151 spatial or temporal scopes (e.g., taxon checklists in protected areas, atlas grid cell summary
152 data). The more complex the sampling design is (from elementary to extended and compilation
153 inventories), the more information about the data collection process needs to be captured to

154 maximise the reusability of these data (Figure 1). Creating a standardised way of recording
 155 these complex data was the overarching goal for creating the Humboldt Extension.

156

157 **Figure 1.** Overview of the four main survey types, illustrating the types of information that can now be
 158 reported using the Humboldt Extension: location and time of recorded taxa, spatiotemporal scope, expected
 159 taxa, protocol used, sampling design, counts of organisms and information about abundance, sampling
 160 effort, absent taxa, taxa out of scope, taxonomic completeness and habitat scope. Colours represent related
 161 aspects of survey data (information on location in blue, time and duration in pink, taxa in orange, protocols
 162 in purple, sampling design in green, and effort in yellow). The ‘Incidental records’ example here describes
 163 presence-only data lacking contextual information (data on two incidental observations in the same area at

164 different times). The other types of surveys represented here have information on the protocols used and
165 possess a defined taxonomic, geospatial, and temporal scope. Our 'Elementary survey' example addresses
166 a single sampling event, while the 'Extended survey' example combines two events. Our 'Compilation'
167 example involves multiple data collection processes (multiple sampling events combined with a literature
168 search and checklist data). As the amount of information in a dataset increases, the potential uses of such
169 datasets and the inferences that can be made (e.g., inference about absences, taxon completeness, and
170 abundance trends) also increase. Within the spatio-temporal scope, box outlines indicate the space and
171 time effectively sampled, and grey icons denote species that were present but not detected. Question marks
172 indicate lack of information. Created with BioRender.com.

173 Augmenting the DwC Standard with the Humboldt Extension

174 Moving from the proposed Humboldt Core (Guralnick et al. 2018) to the ratified Humboldt
175 Extension to Darwin Core occurred in five distinct phases during 2021–2024: i) formation of a
176 TDWG task group to review and progress the Humboldt Core, ii) determination of whether
177 'Humboldt Core' should be presented as a new standard (e.g., a 'core') or as an extension to
178 DwC, iii) review of the Humboldt vocabulary following TDWG standards, iv) implementation and
179 evaluation of the proposed vocabulary with real-world data, and v) ratification following the TDWG
180 process (Vocabulary Maintenance Specification Task Group 2017). See Supplementary Material
181 A for details about the process.

182 Development of the Humboldt Extension began in 2021 under the auspices of TDWG, through
183 the Humboldt Task Group (<https://www.tdwg.org/community/osr/humboldt-extension/>). The Task
184 Group determined that the scope and terms of the proposed Humboldt Core were best suited as
185 an extension to DwC (see Supplementary Material A). Hence, we reviewed the 94 terms initially
186 proposed in the Humboldt Core (Supplementary Material in Guralnick et al. 2018), reformulating
187 term definitions, comments, and examples to follow TDWG standards and current DwC patterns.

188 Following Guralnick et al. (2018) we identified the key descriptors of the data collection process
189 and defined six classes of information that need to be covered by at least one term to ensure the
190 interpretability of a survey: spatial scope, temporal scope, taxonomic and organismal scope,
191 sampling design, sampling protocols, and sampling effort. We defined new terms where gaps in
192 coverage were identified and removed other terms to reduce redundancy and to avoid the use of
193 terms describing summaries and/or interpretations of the data collected (Sica et al. 2022). We
194 presented an initial set of 45 terms for implementation and evaluation with real-world datasets.
195 Testing these datasets provided explicit feedback about vocabulary completeness and clarity,
196 and resulted in enlarging the vocabulary to 54 terms (Hochachka et al. 2023). Three datasets
197 were selected as case studies to illustrate the broad applicability of the Humboldt Extension (see
198 Supplementary Material B).

199 To pursue ratification of the Humboldt Extension (*i.e.*, formalisation of the extension through the
200 TDWG process), we submitted the vocabulary for public review, in response to which several
201 modifications were made. After a 6-month community review, the Humboldt Extension for
202 Ecological Inventories (<https://eco.tdwg.org/>), encompassing a final list of 55 terms, was officially
203 ratified in February 2024. The extension is actively maintained by the Darwin Core Maintenance
204 Group (<https://www.tdwg.org/community/dwc/>), and ongoing feedback can be provided at the
205 extension's GitHub site (<https://github.com/tdwg/hc>).

206 Results

207 Humboldt Extension for Ecological Inventories

208 The Humboldt Extension for Ecological Inventories allows the reporting of six different aspects
209 of the data collection process in a structured manner (Figure 2). The 55 Humboldt Extension
210 terms can be used alongside the existing DwC terms, including those from other standards and

211 extensions (e.g., Extended Measurement or Fact: see
212 https://rs.gbif.org/extension/obis/extended_measurement_or_fact_2023-08-28.xml, Audiovisual
213 Core: Audiovisual Core Maintenance Group 2023, Camtrap DP: Bubnicki et al. 2024). Twenty-
214 three terms have equivalents that allow linking to an externally described object via an
215 Internationalised Resource Identifier (IRI). To avoid information loss or misinterpretation, the
216 details of the data collection process have to be reported at all relevant levels of the hierarchical
217 sampling design (if any). Hence, many terms can be documented at any hierarchical level. The
218 Humboldt Extension includes guidelines on how to structure and utilise hierarchies to describe
219 surveys (TDWG Humboldt Extension Task Group 2024, Table S1 in Supplementary Material A).

220 Below, we describe how the Humboldt Extension enables reporting of the data collection
221 process. Some Humboldt Extension terms partially overlap with DwC Event terms (e.g.,
222 *dwc:samplingEffort*) but allow more granularity in the reporting. The more specific Humboldt
223 terms (e.g., *samplingEffortValue*, *samplingEffortUnit*, *samplingEffortProtocol*) should be used
224 where there is such an overlap. The term descriptions presented in this paper should be
225 complemented by the definitions and specifications of the terms included in the Humboldt
226 Extension Quick Reference Guide (<https://eco.tdwg.org/terms/>). Although the Quick Reference
227 Guide divides the vocabulary into eight groups, we have summarised the terms under six
228 categories, which more naturally follow the logic of someone collecting data. Note that while we
229 have organised our presentation of the Humboldt Extension's terms into categories, these
230 categories do not represent formal DwC classes. Humboldt Extension term names below are
231 written in italics.

232 Capturing the sampling design

233 DwC enables reporting of hierarchically nested survey designs, represented as a relational
234 schema, characterised by parent-child relationships (e.g., a parent sampling event—plot—linked

235 to one or more child sub-sampling events—traps) using event and parent event identifiers. Two
236 Humboldt Extension terms provide a means by which to share additional context to describe this
237 structure (*siteNestingDescription*; e.g., traps nested within transects nested within plots) and
238 report the number of sites surveyed (*siteCount*). These terms can be documented at any
239 hierarchical level.

240 Two additional terms capture information about the survey sites, such as the site names
241 (*verbatimSiteNames*) and descriptions (*verbatimSiteDescriptions*).

242 Spatial scope

243 Several DwC terms already capture the location where observations are made or
244 samples/measurements are taken (e.g., *decimalLatitude*, *decimalLongitude*,
245 *coordinateUncertaintyInMeters*, etc.). The Humboldt Extension adds to these DwC terms by
246 including two sets of paired terms that capture the geospatial scope of the survey, *i.e.* the area
247 expected to be sampled (*geospatialAreaScopeValue* and *geospatialAreaScopeUnit*), and the
248 realised survey area, *i.e.* the area effectively sampled (*totalAreaSampledValue* and
249 *totalAreaSampledUnit*). An additional pair of terms can be used to report habitat types
250 specifically targeted or excluded from sampling (*targetHabitatScope*, *excludedHabitatScope*).

251 Temporal scope

252 Several DwC terms already capture the time when observations are made or
253 samples/measurements are taken (e.g., *eventDate*, *eventTime*). The Humboldt Extension adds
254 a pair of terms (*eventDurationValue*, *eventDurationUnit*) that report the duration of a sampling
255 event at any level of the hierarchy where the duration is needed.

256 Taxonomic and organismal scopes

257 Information on the taxonomic group(s) targeted for and excluded from sampling can now be
258 captured using two terms (*targetTaxonomicScope*, *excludedTaxonomicScope*). Whether every
259 taxon included in the taxonomic scope that was observed or sampled is also reported (*i.e.*,
260 completeness of reporting) can be declared using the term *isTaxonomicScopeFullyReported*.

261 Taxa deemed absent during a survey can be reported at any taxonomic level using two terms:
262 *isAbsenceReported*, *absentTaxa*. Absence refers to the absence of reporting (*i.e.*, taxa not
263 reported), which may be the result of three separate processes: (1) true absence, definitive
264 absence of a taxon in the specified scope at the site at the time of surveying, (2) non-detection,
265 where the taxon was not detected by the sampling gear and effort at the site at the time of
266 surveying, or (3) incomplete reporting, lack of reporting of a taxon that was present and
267 detected, either because that taxon was outside the intended scope of the survey or simply
268 because its presence was not recorded or reported. True absence of a taxon is hard to prove
269 with complete certainty, but a combination of standardised information about taxonomic scope,
270 sampling effort and reporting completeness (that is now enabled by multiple terms in the
271 Extension) can be used to make inferences about true absence. If the absent taxon is within the
272 taxonomic scope of the survey, the sampling protocol and effort are properly designed to
273 sample the taxon, and the reporting of taxa is complete within that scope, then formal statistical
274 methods exist for estimating the probability that a taxon is truly absent (*e.g.*, MacKenzie et al.
275 2002).

276 If taxonomic completeness (*i.e.*, how comprehensively an area has been surveyed) was
277 assessed, both the results and the protocols employed to determine this can also be
278 documented using the terms *taxonCompletenessReported* and *taxonCompletenessProtocols*.

279 Four terms are available to report the existence of non-target taxa and/or organisms (a.k.a.
280 bycatch) in a dataset: *hasNonTargetTaxa*, *nonTargetTaxa*, *areNonTargetTaxaFullyReported*,
281 and *hasNonTargetOrganisms*.

282 As some taxa undergo dramatic morphological and physiological transformations during their
283 lifetime (e.g., corals, butterflies and moths, amphibians), 9 terms are available to report targeted
284 (or excluded) organismal life stages, as well as growth forms and/or degrees of establishment:
285 *targetLifeStageScope*, *excludedLifeStageScope*, *isLifeStageScopeFullyReported*,
286 *targetDegreeOfEstablishmentScope*, *excludedDegreeOfEstablishmentScope*,
287 *isDegreeOfEstablishmentScopeFullyReported*, *targetGrowthFormScope*,
288 *excludedGrowthFormScope*, *isGrowthFormScopeFullyReported*. Other target traits not captured
289 by these three categories (e.g., freshwater macroinvertebrates or small mammals) can be
290 captured in *verbatimTargetScope*.

291 Sampling protocols and survey type

292 Protocols and specific methodologies for sampling or collecting measurements during a survey
293 can be reported using three terms: *protocolNames*, *protocolDescriptions*, and
294 *protocolReferences*.

295 A series of terms are available to describe if abundance information was collected and reported
296 (*isAbundanceReported*), if there was any cap on abundance value (*isAbundanceCapReported*,
297 *abundanceCap*), how organism counts were reported when a taxon could be reported at more
298 than one taxonomic level such as species and subspecies using
299 *isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive* (see specific guidelines on usage of this term
300 here: <https://eco.tdwg.org/inclusive/>), and if vegetation cover was reported
301 (*isVegetationCoverReported*).

302 Four terms are available to report if specimen vouchers or material samples were collected
303 (*hasMaterialSamples* and *hasVouchers*), what those samples were (*materialSampleTypes*), and
304 where any vouchers are housed (*voucherInstitutions*).

305 Finally, three terms expand on the DwC Event term *eventType*. If the data reported is a survey
306 or inventory, the search or data collection process employed can be documented in
307 *inventoryTypes*. If the survey is a compilation of multiple datasets, detailed information can be
308 captured on whether the data originates from sampling events, ancillary data compiled from
309 other sources, or a combination of both, using the terms *compilationTypes* and
310 *compilationSourceTypes*.

311 Sampling effort

312 Information about the sampling effort (*i.e.*, the intensity of the sampling process) can be
313 captured with five terms at any hierarchical level. Whether or not sampling effort is reported, and
314 what that effort was, can be reported using *isSamplingEffortReported* and the paired terms
315 *samplingEffortValue* and *samplingEffortUnit*. Specific details about the methods implemented
316 can be reported in *samplingEffortProtocol*. Importantly, the people and/or organisations
317 responsible for conducting the survey can now be captured using *samplingPerformedBy*, both
318 as free text and, ideally, by including permanent identifiers for these entities (*e.g.*, Open
319 Researcher and Contributor ID – ORCID, Research Organization Registry – ROR). Since
320 weather and other conditions can affect the probability of detecting and identifying an organism,
321 which in turn can impact the resulting effort, two terms help describe weather conditions during
322 the survey and extreme weather events (*reportedWeather*, *reportedExtremeConditions*).

323

Humboldt Extension for Ecological Inventories		
Protocols protocolDescriptions protocolNames protocolReferences isAbundanceReported isAbundanceCapReported abundanceCap isLeastSpecificTargetCategoryQuantityInclusive isVegetationCoverReported hasMaterialSamples materialSampleTypes hasVouchers voucherInstitutions inventoryTypes compilationTypes compilationSourceTypes	Spatial scope geospatialScopeAreaUnit geospatialScopeAreaValue totalAreaSampledUnit totalAreaSampledValue targetHabitatScope excludedHabitatScope	Taxonomic & organismal scope targetTaxonomicScope excludedTaxonomicScope isAbsenceReported absentTaxa isTaxonomicScopeFullyReported taxonCompletenessReported taxonCompletenessProtocols hasNonTargetTaxa nonTargetTaxa areNonTargetTaxaFullyReported hasNonTargetOrganisms targetDegreeOfEstablishmentScope excludedDegreeOfEstablishmentScope isDegreeOfEstablishmentScopeFullyReported targetGrowthFormScope excludedGrowthFormScope isGrowthFormScopeFullyReported targetLifeStageScope excludedLifeStageScope isLifeStageScopeFullyReported verbatimTargetScope
	Temporal scope eventDurationUnit eventDurationValue	
	Effort isSamplingEffortReported samplingEffortValue samplingEffortUnit samplingEffortProtocol reportedWeather reportedExtremeConditions samplingPerformedBy	
Sampling design siteCount siteNestingDescription verbatimSiteDescriptions verbatimSiteNames		

324

325 **Figure 2.** 55 Humboldt Extension terms organised in six non-formal categories that capture different

326 aspects of the data collection process. Created with BioRender.com.

327 Case studies

328 We illustrate the application of the Humboldt Extension using three case studies in a
 329 supplement to this paper (Table 1, Supplementary Material B). The first case study describes
 330 Antarctic marine inventory data (Van De Putte et al. 2010), which includes multiple target and
 331 organismal scopes and exemplifies the use of multiple extensions to properly describe such a
 332 complex dataset. The second case study illustrates the importance of describing variation in
 333 sampling methods among observers taking part in a global citizen/participatory science project
 334 (Sullivan et al. 2009, 2014). The third example highlights the ability of the Humboldt Extension
 335 to describe complex, hierarchical sampling designs in data collected using a diversity of planned
 336 methods to survey different taxa (<https://www.rapidinventories.fieldmuseum.org>). These case
 337 studies demonstrate the flexibility and comprehensiveness of the Humboldt Extension in
 338 describing real-world datasets, highlighting how survey information beyond the species
 339 occurrence can be captured in a structured way (Table 1).

Type of Information	Reason for the addition	Case studies
<p>What taxa or organisms were the targets of the survey? Were there any taxa or organisms intentionally excluded from the scope of the survey?</p>	<p>The types of organisms that are in the scope of the survey can be described with Humboldt Extension terms not only taxonomically (<i>e.g.</i>, which species?) but also based on other criteria such as life stage (<i>e.g.</i>, larva or adult) or other defined groupings (<i>e.g.</i>, by size or ecological functionality). It can also be important to report which types of organisms are excluded from the scope of the survey (<i>e.g.</i>, because of limitations in the sampling instrument used).</p>	<p>Case study 1: OBIS</p>
<p>Were any non-target organisms detected and reported?</p>	<p>While a survey will typically be intended to detect and record specific types of organisms, potentially non-target organisms will also be detected. If desired, these non-target organisms or bycatch can be reported using the Humboldt Extension.</p>	<p>Case study 1: OBIS Case study 3: Field Museum Rapid Inventories</p>
<p>Which taxa were the targets of the survey, but were not detected during a survey event?</p>	<p>Data about the failure to detect a taxon, when that taxon was in the scope of the survey, is important for many types of analytical methods. With the Humboldt Extension, records of zero individuals do not need to be explicitly entered as such but can be indicated implicitly when the taxonomic scope is reported and when all detected taxa are indicated as being reported (<i>i.e.</i>, completeness of reporting).</p>	<p>Case study 1: OBIS Case study 2: eBird</p>

Within one sampling event, were there differences in survey protocol among records?	When sampling protocols are not tightly constrained, for example, for data collected in citizen science surveys, some aspects of the data collection process can differ among sampling events in a survey (e.g., sampling effort). Such differences can be reported using the Humboldt Extension. Accounting for these variations improves the precision and accuracy of model estimates.	Case study 2: eBird Case study 3: Field Museum Rapid Inventories
Are multiple surveys, each focused on a different target organism type and with different sampling methodology, related to each other (e.g., same sampling locations, same sampling dates)?	Community and ecosystem surveys may need to employ different sampling protocols for different types of organisms or may require a structured spatial or temporal design. The Humboldt Extension allows information from different sampling events to be linked with each other in a hierarchical manner (e.g., different survey protocols conducted at the same location at the same time or a spatially nested sampling design).	Case study 3: Field Museum Rapid Inventories

341 **Table 1:** The Humboldt Extension enables researchers to store multiple types of information about
342 surveys as data that can be searched and sorted. Previously, this contextual information was only
343 contained in metadata documentation. In this table, we illustrate some important types of information that
344 can now be reported making use of Humboldt Extension terms. Examples of data sources for which
345 Humboldt Extension terms describe important facets of data are described as Case studies in
346 Supplementary Material B.

347 Discussion

348 The Humboldt Extension was developed to capture and represent a broad array of biodiversity
349 data collected through standardised, structured or semi-structured methods, including museum
350 expeditions, biodiversity surveys using direct observations, semi-structured monitoring such as

351 eBird checklists, eDNA, camera traps, acoustic monitoring, or any other ecological monitoring
352 initiatives. It also accommodates data collected in an unstructured way from citizen science
353 efforts, bioblitzes, or other opportunistic sampling. A large amount of biodiversity survey data is
354 produced by ecological research, but its availability is limited as it often depends on the
355 motivations of the data collector and the constraints on reporting and sharing (Bowler et al.
356 2025). Whilst some of these data are shared and compiled in biodiversity databases, such as
357 the Living Planet Database (WWF 2024), Predicts (Hudson et al. 2014), and BioTime (Dornelas
358 et al. 2018), the vast majority is stored in repositories as ancillary data to scientific articles
359 where they are typically discoverable through dataset catalogues and supplementary materials
360 to publications, limiting their discoverability and reuse (Huang et al. 2012). Much data are not
361 shared at all, only existing in the possession of the data collectors (Huang et al. 2012), which
362 increases the risk of loss due to local storage failures or ageing technology (Gonzalez and
363 Peres-Neto 2015). As policymakers increasingly rely on biodiversity data to inform decision-
364 making and conservation, the adoption of standardised vocabularies that enhance data
365 interpretability and reuse becomes imperative. Features of the Humboldt Extension can
366 encourage biodiversity data reuse by: (1) enabling easier discovery and interpretability of data,
367 (2) facilitating integration of data from multiple sources, and (3) incentivising data sharing.

368 **Enabling biodiversity data discovery and interpretability**

369 The terms in the Humboldt Extension provide a standardised way for researchers to describe
370 their data and metadata, so that people have a common understanding of the dataset (*e.g.*,
371 what was intended to be sampled, how it was collected, and by whom) while being in a
372 machine-readable form. Four important types of information about surveys can now be more
373 properly structured and reported for each dataset: (1) hierarchical events and relationships
374 among records, (2) a richer description of the data collection process and sources of variation

375 that can affect the probability of organisms being detected, and (3) the taxonomic completeness
376 of the data reported, all of which are only interpretable because of (4) information concerning
377 the survey scopes (*i.e.*, taxonomic scope, target spatial and temporal resolution). By adding
378 terms that convey the dataset's spatiotemporal scope, sampling effort, and taxonomic
379 completeness, the Humboldt Extension facilitates indexing of this information in databases and
380 enables potential data users to filter, search and use information that was previously buried in
381 metadata text files and other ancillary documentation.

382 While the Humboldt Extension allows the informed integration of survey data, the expanded
383 range of information may require more detailed steps in data discovery and analysis. For
384 example, when searching for available data, researchers could consider restricting themselves
385 to using data from surveys that provide complete reports of all taxa (within a defined scope) so
386 that information on non-detections is available or can be inferred. If so, they will then need to
387 decide whether to search for specific ranges of survey effort and protocols to aid in the process
388 of inferring whether the non-detections indicate true absence of taxa. This added capability,
389 enabled by the Humboldt Extension, may create more overhead for users to discover data, but it
390 also provides needed information that was previously unavailable in the more limited vocabulary
391 available in DwC and currently used in data discovery platforms such as GBIF and OBIS.
392 Critically, Humboldt Extension and DwC are meant to be used together so species lists and
393 metadata about those lists' survey protocols remain conjoined.

394 Facilitating the integration of data from multiple sources

395 The information contained using Humboldt Extension terms creates the opportunity to search for
396 data collected within a user-specified range of protocols, allowing for the best possible approach
397 to be used in the analysis of biodiversity data. Potentially, survey data could be directly

398 combined if they follow similar, widely adopted data collection protocols. However, more
399 complex integration of data following different protocols is also possible. By statistically
400 modelling the effects of differences in data types and protocols, accuracy can be maximised and
401 uncertainty can be appropriately captured (Adjei et al. 2023, Fletcher et al. 2019, Mäkinen et al.
402 2024). This should enable more comprehensive prediction of species abundance or occurrence
403 for a full geographic and taxonomic scope, with applications such as the development of
404 Species Population EBVs (Jetz et al. 2019).

405 The lack of data standards and data models for biodiversity surveys is also a barrier to
406 integrating survey data with qualitatively different data types, such as species traits and
407 environmental data (Guralnick et al. 2018, Huang et al. 2012). The availability and volume of
408 remotely sensed data that measure different aspects of the environment have increased since
409 the 1970s, with an increased resolution from pixel widths of kilometres to less than a meter
410 (Mathieu and Aubrecht 2018). However, higher integration with *in-situ* biodiversity surveys is
411 needed to significantly improve the monitoring of ecosystems or species habitats (Luque et al.
412 2018). The spatial resolution of biodiversity data (particularly for incidental records) is generally
413 low or not reported at all, and locations are recorded with high uncertainty (Bloom et al. 2018),
414 which makes it difficult to align with the latest remotely sensed products. Having clearly defined
415 terms to address the spatial extent and resolution of biodiversity data can aid in: (1) highlighting
416 the higher resolution at which many surveys are carried out, (2) validating remotely sensed data
417 with *in situ* biodiversity data, and (3) better informing models that integrate environmental and
418 species level data about the accuracy of their results.

419 Incentivising data sharing

420 The ability to reliably credit data collectors for their work has the potential to change the
421 incentive structure and create a cultural shift toward open science (Groom et al. 2020). Current

422 open data infrastructures already enable data providers to be acknowledged for their
423 contributions via dataset Digital Object Identifier (DOI) citation. The Humboldt Extension
424 enhances this further by allowing the proper attribution of the actual data collectors
425 (*samplingPerformedBy* term). By providing this possibility, we hope to encourage the ecological
426 community to make their data more accessible by sharing their surveys following FAIR
427 principles.

428 Community development and maintenance of the Humboldt 429 Extension

430 The Humboldt Extension is already ratified as an international biodiversity standard, it is already
431 implemented in GBIF and can be readily incorporated into other biodiversity platforms (e.g.,
432 OBIS, Map of Life) as well as in field data collection systems (e.g., BioCollect) or other database
433 structures (e.g., the Field Museum database). We acknowledge that it has not been tested with
434 all potential biodiversity survey types, nor do the terms within the Humboldt Extension cover all
435 facets of a biodiversity survey (e.g., only some of the unbounded number of possible target
436 scopes are covered). Expanding the Extension's capabilities remains possible by developing
437 and adding new terms and even new structures to cover further aspects of biodiversity datasets.

438 With the initial version in place and validated by the wider biodiversity community, the addition
439 of further terms to support the reporting of specific data is streamlined. Initiatives to develop
440 standards or structures for storing other types of survey information are also underway. For
441 example, GBIF is leading an initiative to expand the structural capabilities of data sharing via
442 DwC (see <https://www.gbif.org/new-data-model>). Structurally, a survey, supported by the terms
443 of the Humboldt Extension, is an entirely new DwC class in this new data model. Further, this
444 new data model generalises Humboldt's concept of target scopes, allowing any scope or

445 number of scopes to be defined and included. A known shortcoming of the current state of the
446 Humboldt Extension (and of many other extensions) is the need to develop controlled
447 vocabularies for well-known biodiversity sampling methods and protocols, which would improve
448 the ability of data users to filter datasets based on common protocols. To foster the
449 development and maintenance of community-driven controlled vocabularies or other
450 terminologies, the DwC Maintenance Group of TDWG will maintain the Humboldt Extension
451 and, together with GBIF, will engage with the biodiversity and ecology communities to continue
452 its ongoing evolution and fitness for purpose (Ingenloff 2025; Ingenloff et al. 2025).

453 Conclusion

454 The GBF, as well as other global treaties focused on biological diversity, emphasises the need
455 for improved biodiversity monitoring data from local to national levels, and information sharing to
456 support global decision-making. It is not sufficient to simply increase the quantity of monitoring
457 data; more data may make the proper downstream processing more complicated. Instead, what
458 is needed are ways to ensure monitoring data is in formats that require minimal effort for use in
459 downstream analytical pipelines. The Humboldt Extension for Ecological Inventories can be a
460 key contribution to this streamlining and improvement effort, as it can be implemented in
461 national biodiversity data infrastructures to support their data collection systems and databases,
462 encouraging data collectors to share their data following Open Science and FAIR principles.
463 However, it is up to the data collectors, researchers, data managers and aggregators to
464 maximise its use. We call for all individuals and institutions involved in biodiversity monitoring to
465 utilise data standards and, in particular, work with the standards community to map their
466 monitoring schemas to this Extension. This effort will ensure that biodiversity data is accessible
467 for the benefit of the whole of society; data managers can improve the curation and
468 maintenance of natural history collections, researchers can provide more robust assessments

469 and modelled predictions, policymakers can make data-informed decisions, and civil society can
470 benefit from an improved collective understanding of biodiversity status and trends.

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